

4C

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_873 CD11_GRI.fcs
Ungated
55123

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_873 CD11_GRI.fcs
Cells
19253

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_873 CD11_GRI.fcs
eGFP+
19101

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_1390 GRI_CD11 FOR SCATTER.f
Ungated
80598

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_1390 GRI_CD11 FOR SCATTER.f
Cells
17050

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_1390 GRI_CD11 FOR SCATTER.f
eGFP+
16779

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_1391 GRI_CD11 FOR SCATTER.f
Ungated
87362

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_1391 GRI_CD11 FOR SCATTER.f
Cells
17446

26-05-14 mBM 4x PLDLS ZEO_1391 GRI_CD11 FOR SCATTER.f
eGFP+
17318

5H

Sample Name	Subset Name	Count
mix experiment all sample_SB 1564_1581 Day 14.fcs	Ungated	40817

Sample Name	Subset Name	Count
mix experiment all sample_SB 1564_1581 Day 14.fcs	live gate	28749

mix experiment all sample_SB 1564_1581 Day 14.fcs
live gate
28749